

Book Review

Gateways to the Sea: Historic Ports and Docks of Mumbai Region

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Beneath the “meta-narrative” of cosmopolitan cities which are centres of trade, commerce, socialising, cultures, and politics the sensitive scholar perceives localities and their histories as rich in sociological and economic details. This book illustrates that all great cities are palimpsests of geographies and histories and Mumbai, for long called Bombay, is no exception. Of all Indian cosmopolises perhaps Mumbai is the most modern and this fact is highlighted by its having been an emporium of maritime and inland trade since time immemorial. Therefore, it is right to say that since ancient times it has been a “magnet for voyagers and traders from different parts of the world” and its localities are mentioned in Indian and non-Indian ancient sources.

Researching a city means understanding the confluence of archaeology, geography, and inter-disciplinary history including visual and oral history. This holistic paradigm of urban history informs the volume under review. A study of the historiography of the lesser-known ports north and south of Mumbai proper unveils the “intricate networks of ancient trade routes” at the regional and international levels. These ports were links between Europe, Asia, and the Konkan coast.

Since ports and docks are central to a maritime coastal city, we should know who built them at various points in time. The resident subaltern seafaring communities like the *Kolis* and migrants like the *Brahmins*, *Patbans*, and *Malis* who arrived on the coastal belt from distant places are mentioned in this excellent volume. Since the reclamations and docks of Mumbai owe their origins to many enterprising individuals, men like Bhau Laxman Ajinkya, after whom the popular *Bhaucha Dhakka* [Ferry Wharf built in 1841] is named, are written about. If you see Mumbai not as a single city but as a connection of ports and docks you realise the importance of ferries and wharves to the region's economic and social life. In fact, the entire Konkan coast is inconceivable without the ubiquitous ferries. Only those who have travelled the length and

breadth of the north Konkan coast can truly appreciate this; quotidian life is impossible to imagine and live without the ferries. The maps and photographs that embellish this well-researched volume highlight this for the lay reader. They will refresh the memory of anyone who has used these ferries as this reviewer did during a Konkan fieldwork trip in 2020.

The language of the volume is simple and free of jargon and this enhances the academic importance of the book without making it pretentious.

A well written foreword and introduction stimulate the reader's excitement. The glossary and index have been carefully drafted with the former enriching our knowledge of etymology. For example, did we know that the *ghurab* is an Arabian sea going ship called so in Arabic because its distinctive prow resembles a raven? No doubt the *ghurab* is mentioned in the sources as a fast-sailing vessel adapted to the Arabian Sea and the Indian Ocean.

The book is a treasure trove for the scholar of maritime affairs. It is “shaped” by a “spirit of revival and re-animation” and follows a “multi-disciplinary” approach to maritime history. “How have post-colonial development and priorities altered and expanded marine related infrastructure” is a question that animates many essays in the volume as the foreword tells us. This carefully crafted book asserts that beneath the “meta-narrative” of Mumbai, with all its commercial and political implications for Indian history, rich local narratives have awaited discovery for a long time.” Thus, the scholars associated with this book have filled a chasm in the overall historiography of Mumbai a city that offers much more than Bollywood to the perceptive observer.

The book is divided into four balanced sections, as follows:

- 1) Part A looks at the ports north of Mumbai like Sopara, Vasai, Versova, Madh Island, and Mahim. People have often heard of these places but are unfamiliar with their histories which are revealed in these chapters in rich detail. The origin, rise, and

- fall of these “lost” ports are documented in these fascinating chapters.
- 2) Part B concentrates attention on the docks of Mumbai like Mazagaon Dock whose history of shipbuilding goes back to 1774. Also critically surveyed are the Bhaucha Dhakka, Bombay Port, the Marine Yard and Naval Dockyard, and the famous Sassoon Dock.
 - 3) Part C has chapters on the ports and docks East of Mumbai like Kalyan, Thana, Panvel, and the Jawaharlal Nehru Port. Why did these ports come into existence and what was traded through them are the questions answered in this part. In fact, in all the ports rice, salt, grain, and cloth trade was important both from the viewpoint of overseas and intra-local coastal trade which was geographically linked to inland trade via rivers and mountain passes. Precolonial sources are rich in information about such trade which generated handsome profits for Indian and foreign traders alike. Opium was another profit generating commodity traded from Bombay and made many Parsis rich and influential in the 19th Century.
 - 4) Part D analyses the ports and docks south of Mumbai like Alibag, Thal, Mandwa, Rewas, Chaul, Janjira, and Rajapuri. The history of these ports has been “imbricated with the maritime history of Mumbai” since the medieval period.

The riveting history of the Mughals, Sidis, Marathas, English, and Portuguese which happened on the Konkan Coast during the 17th and 18th Centuries cannot be written without reference to these ports. The architecture of the coastal forts of the Konkan “displays the rich palimpsest of cultures” and “syncretic culture” which underlines the medieval history of the Deccan.

The ‘introduction’ claims that the “history of ports in the Mumbai region is not only about commerce and trade, but also replete with military exploits and naval battles, piracy, and perfidy, fierce political rivalries, and conquests, all for the control of this coastal jewel, its abundant resources, and its many flourishing ports.” No doubt, Bombay became the financial and industrial hub of British colonial power in India.

The chapters of the volume justify the claims made by the three editors in a well-written Introduction. This book would be useful to anyone interested in Mumbai’s past but it comprises a multi-coloured treasure trove for those teachers and students of Indian history who search for non-elitist histories not framed in the ideological binaries of our times.

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‘Gateways to the Sea’ is a compilation of essays, that illuminates for the reader the history of the Maharashtra and Konkan coastal regions from every perspective — geopolitical, geographic, economic, cultural, people, land, rivers, estuaries, and sailing vessels. The fertile hinterland had an abundance of agricultural produce like mangoes, coconuts, and spices, while artisans and crafts persons created products like cotton cloth, cartwheels, jewellery, and gems, which were prized in markets as far as the Arab lands and beyond, to Greece and Rome. ‘Gateways to the Sea’ explores the fascinating growth of ports including Sopara, Vasai, Mahim, Thane, Kalyan, and Chaul, and the numerous forts, at harbour mouths, and the hinterland.

-Admiral VS Shekhawat

Contributors

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Ports and Docks are the hubs around which the lives of coastal communities are built. As centres of commerce, trade, and enterprise, they attract travellers and merchants from around the world. Some of the ancient ports in Mumbai and its surrounding districts have archaeological evidence of trade with Greece and Rome. There is a history of trade with the Arabs in medieval times, and with Portuguese, Dutch, and British seafarers in more recent times. Trade created coastal cities and townships of wealth and power and cosmopolitan cultures. Colonial invaders tussled with the regional ruling powers – most notably the Marathas – for supremacy, to control these ports.

Over time, these thriving ports have decayed and, with the siltation of river mouths and creeks, some ancient ports are now lost to antiquity.

It is important for future generations to be aware of the illustrious past of the Ports and Docks of the coast in and around Mumbai. This book is an endeavour by eminent authors to record the history of seventeen of these ports and docks.

